

Factorial and Multinomial Theorem on the Binomial Coefficients for Combinatorial Geometric Series

Chinnaraji Annamalai
 School of Management, Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur, India
 Email: anna@iitkgp.ac.in
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0992-2584>

Abstract: This paper presents a multinomial theorem on the binomial coefficients for combinatorial geometric series. The coefficient for each term in combinatorial geometric series refers to a binomial coefficient. These ideas can enable the scientific researchers to solve the real life problems.

MSC Classification codes: 05A10, 40A05 (65B10)

Keywords: computation, combinatorics, binomial expansion

1. Introduction

When the author of this article was trying to develop the multiple summations of geometric series, a new idea was stimulated his mind to create a combinatorial geometric series [1-9]. The combinatorial geometric series is a geometric series whose coefficient of each term of the geometric series denotes the binomial coefficient V_n^r . In this article, binomial identities and multinomial theorem is provided using the binomial coefficients for combinatorial geometric series.

2. Combinatorial Geometric Series

The combinatorial geometric series [1-9] is derived from the multiple summations of geometric series. The coefficient of each term in the combinatorial refers to the binomial coefficient V_n^r .

$$\sum_{i_1=0}^n \sum_{i_2=i_1}^n \sum_{i_3=i_2}^n \cdots \sum_{i_r=i_{r-1}}^n x^{i_r} = \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i \quad \& \quad V_n^r = \frac{(n+1)(n+2)(n+3) \cdots (n+r-1)(n+r)}{r!},$$

where $n \geq 0, r \geq 1$ and $n, r \in N = \{0, 1, 2, 3, \dots\}$.

Here, $\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i$ refers to the combinatorial geometric series and

V_n^r is the binomial coefficient for combinatorial geometric series.

Theorem: $\frac{(n^2)!}{(n!)^n} = V_n^{(n-1)n} \times V_n^{(n-2)n} \times V_n^{(n-3)n} \times \cdots \times V_n^n, \quad (n \geq 0 \ \& \ k, n \in N).$

Proof. Let us prove this theorems using the following theorem.

For any k nonnegative integers n_1, n_2, n_3, \dots and n_k ,

$$\frac{(n_1 + n_2 + n_3 + \cdots + n_k)!}{(n_1! n_2! n_3! \cdots n_k!)} = V_{n_1}^{n_2+n_3+\cdots+n_k} \times V_{n_2}^{n_3+n_4+\cdots+n_k} \times V_{n_3}^{n_4+n_5+\cdots+n_k} \times \cdots \times V_{n_{k-1}}^{n_k};$$

$$\frac{(n+p+r)!}{n!p!r!} = V_n^{p+r} \times V_p^r \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{(n+r)!}{n!r!} = V_n^r.$$

If $n_1 = n_2 = n_3 = \dots = n_k = n$, then $\frac{(kn)!}{(n!)^k} = V_n^{(k-1)n} \times V_n^{(k-2)n} \times V_n^{(k-3)n} \times \dots \times V_n^n$.

Here, $V_n^{\{k-(k-1)\}n} = V_n^n$; $V_n^{\{k-(k-2)\}n} = V_n^{2n}$; $V_n^{\{k-(k-3)\}n} = V_n^{3n}$; ...

If $n_1 = n_2 = n_3 = \dots = n_n = n$, then $\frac{(n^2)!}{(n!)^n} = V_n^{(n-1)n} \times V_n^{(n-2)n} \times V_n^{(n-3)n} \times \dots \times V_n^n$.

Here, $V_n^{(n-1)n} = \frac{\{n+(n-1)n\}!}{n!(n^2-n)!} = \frac{(n^2)!}{n!(n^2-n)!}$ & $V_n^{(n-k)n} = \frac{\{n+(n-k)n\}!}{n!\{(n-k)n\}!}$.

Conclusion

In this article, a multinomial theorem was built using the binomial theorem on the binomial coefficients for combinatorial geometric series. These ideas can enable the scientific researchers for research and development further.

References

- [1] Annamalai, C. (2022) Binomial Coefficients and Identities in Combinatorial Geometric Series. OSF Preprints. <http://dx.doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/4ha3c>.
- [2] Annamalai, C. (2022) Multinomial Theorem on the Binomial Coefficients for Combinatorial Geometric Series. Zenodo. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7029149>.
- [3] Annamalai, C. (2020) Optimized Computing Technique for Combination in Combinatorics. *hal-0286583*. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/9p4ek>.
- [4] Annamalai, C. (2020) Novel Computing Technique in Combinatorics. *hal-02862222*. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/m9re5>.
- [5] Annamalai, C. (2022) Computation of Combinatorial Geometric Series and its Combinatorial Identities for Machine Learning and Cybersecurity. *COE, Cambridge University Press*. <https://doi.org/10.33774/coe-2022-b6mks>.
- [6] Annamalai, C. (2022) Annamalai's Binomial Identity and Theorem, *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4097907>.
- [7] Annamalai, C. (2022) Computation Method for Combinatorial Geometric Series and its Applications. *COE, Cambridge University Press*. <https://doi.org/10.33774/coe-2022-pnx53-v22>.
- [8] Annamalai, C. (2022) Computing Method for Combinatorial Geometric Series and Binomial Expansion. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4168016>.

- [9] Annamalai, C. (2022) Factorials and Integers for Applications in Computing and Cryptography. *COE, Cambridge University Press*. <https://doi.org/10.33774/coe-2022-b6mks>.